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PECULIARITIES OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM IN RUSSIA

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Abstract

The article considers the system of higher education in Russia, through which cultural experience is transmitted, contributing to the accumulation of intellectual and spiritual potentials. It is shown that the model of the education system is conditioned not only by the needs of social reality and strategic goals of society, but also carries the historical memory of its development and formation. Therefore, in the process of social transformation, the choice of the most adequate model that meets both internal and external needs of the state is an important task that aims to create a clearly functioning mechanism that forms the type of personality that meets the given social order.

Keywords: education, personality, order, memory, history.

I. INTRODUCTION

The process of reforming higher education illustrates the state of Russian society, as the goals, objectives, value component and content of education always correspond with the goals, objectives and needs of society. In this regard, analyzing the reform process in its dynamics, it is possible to reveal the explicit and latent goals of transformation, as well as to identify the level of economic, political, socio-cultural and spiritual level of Russian society. The relevance of the article lies in the fact that through the prism of reforming the system of higher education can be revealed and explained problem areas of society that require close attention. Among them it is possible to single out such spheres as national spiritual culture, which needs strengthening and development, quality of education, employment of young specialists, etc. The main problem is the need to analyze scientifically the problems of higher education system reform. The main problem is the need for scientific analysis of the consequences that entail reforming the system of Russian higher education.

These consequences can be of a fundamental nature, affecting the qualitative characteristics of the intellectual, spiritual and cultural potentials of the nation.

II. METHODOLOGY

The problem is considered within the framework of interdisciplinary approach, which includes several conceptually important provisions. Thus, the research is based on:

- system approach, which assumes the consideration of phenomena, objects and processes as part of a broader and inseparable whole - a system of interrelated elements. In our study the system of Russian higher education is considered as an integral component of the complex of institutional formations of the Russian society, as well as in a broader context - as part of the global system of social relations.

- the doctrine of methodological individualism, which postulates that all sociological conclusions can be based on the characteristics of individuals. This doctrine was formed as an opposition to the doctrine of E. Durkheim, who argued that within the framework of sociological analysis the characteristics of individuals can be neglected and "social facts" exist independently and are studied independently of the individuals whose actions they determine.

III. RESULTS

According to the "Law on Education" (2012), higher education aims to ensure the training of highly qualified personnel in all major areas of socially useful activities in accordance with the needs of society and the state, meeting the needs of the individual in intellectual, cultural and moral development, deepening and expanding education, scientific and pedagogical qualification.

The question of the beginning of university education in Russia is still among the debatable ones. According to Doctor of Historical Sciences Anatoly Avrus, the history of Russian universities should begin with February 8 (January 28, old style) 1724, when the Senate adopted a decree on the establishment of the Academy of Sciences with St. Petersburg University and Gymnasium, and January 7, 1726 (December 27, 1725, old style) was the official opening of the Academy. But the idea of the need to create a university had arisen much earlier, when Boris Godunov in 1600 sent John Kramer to Germany to find and bring professors to Moscow. However, resistance from the clergy forced Boris Godunov to abandon the idea. Soon after his accession to the throne, False Dmitry I spoke in favor of establishing a university, but he did not have time to realize his plans.

In the XVIII century there was another significant event for Russian higher education: January 23 (January 12, O.S.), 1755 Elizabeth Petrovna signed a decree on the founding of the Moscow University, the task of which was "to grow in the space of our empire any useful knowledge in the way of decent sciences. The university was open to people from different estates, except for serfs.

In the second half of the 18th - first half of the XIX-th century, the need for the development of higher professional education became more and more obvious. In 1733 in St. Petersburg was founded equal to the Academy of Mining School, which laid the foundation for engineering education in Russia. Agricultural, economic, pedagogical, medical, musical, theatrical and artistic, theological, military higher education institutions were also established. In 1895 there were 11 higher technical educational institutions in Russia, and by 1917 there were 183 universities. However, during this period some negative features appeared in the educational policy of the state: girls and representatives of the lower strata were not allowed to study, tuition fees were introduced in universities, which were increased several times during the next 10 years, the category of private students was abolished and access to the university was restricted to outsiders (previously, everyone could attend lectures).

Thus, the right to higher education was restricted and became available to fewer and fewer young people.

A new stage in the development of higher education came after the revolution of 1917. The restructuring of the entire education system began, and the People's Commissariat of Education was established. The government decree of November 22 (November 9, O.S.) 1917 organized the State Commission on Education, whose task was to develop a framework for the construction of a new system of public education. Nationalization of all types of educational institutions began.

On December 24 (December 11, O.S.), 1917, the government adopted a decree "On the transfer of the business of upbringing and education from the clerical department to the People's Commissariat for Education". Later, in 1929, vocational educational institutions were transferred to the jurisdiction of various Commissariats according to their specialty. Class and national restrictions were eliminated, and the previous inequality of women in education was destroyed.

The 1936 Constitution of the USSR (article 121) proclaimed, for the first time in Russian history, the right of USSR citizens to education. This right was ensured by universal compulsory eight-year education, the broad development of general secondary polytechnic education, vocational and technical education, specialized secondary and higher education on the basis of the link between education and life and production, the full development of evening and correspondence education, the free availability of all types of education, the system of State scholarships, mother-tongue instruction in schools, and the organization of free industrial, technical and agronomic training in factories, state farms and collective farms. Article 122 of the Constitution granted women in the USSR equal rights with men in all areas, including education.

By its Decision of March 18, 1965, the Council of Ministers of the USSR granted preferential admission to higher educational institutions on a competitive basis to persons who had at least two years of practical work experience, to military personnel who had been discharged from the reserve, and to persons who had been awarded a gold or silver medal at the end of secondary school or who had graduated from a specialized secondary educational institution and received a diploma with honors.

The 1977 Constitution was an important milestone in consolidating the right of citizens of the USSR to education. In it, the right to education was ensured by the free availability of all types of education, the implementation of universal compulsory secondary education for young people, the broad development of vocational, specialized secondary and higher education on the basis of the link between education and life and production, the development of correspondence and evening education, the provision of State scholarships and benefits to pupils and students, the free issue of school textbooks, the possibility of school instruction in the mother tongue, and the creation of conditions for self-education.

Experts note that in the USSR under the conditions of a planned economy, universities solved specific tasks of a "personnel factory". The models of HEIs, although they had local specifications, were mostly stable. In all Soviet republics since the 1960s three models of HEIs have been distinguished:

- HEIs established according to the territorial-production principle, whose main task was to train personnel for the regional economy. This type of HEIs included pedagogical, medical, polytechnic, as well as those belonging to sectoral departments and ministries (e.g. agricultural). Vertical differentiation within this group of universities was based on the territorial principle.

Metropolitan HEIs performed the function of methodological leadership and personnel support for other HEIs;

- Sectoral HEIs, which focused on training personnel for a certain industry on a national scale. HEIs were embedded in the production process. There were three subtypes of universities in this group: specialized universities - part of the Soviet industrial clusters (e.g., Kazan Aviation Institute); central specialized universities (Moscow Institute of Steel and Alloys); network industrial universities (e.g., railway universities);

- classical universities that trained personnel for science and other universities. First of all, in fundamental disciplines, as well as personnel for local managerial elites. Classical universities could also train teachers.

The planned management of higher education was based on the allocation of student teaching places and their financing according to the needs of specific industries or even specific factories, which was supported by the placement of graduates in wage-controlled jobs. The policy was determined by the Central Committee of the CPSU.

Universities were subordinate to 28 ministries, although the entire legal and regulatory framework was determined by the central governing body (Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education; USSR State Committee for National Education).

Research and scientific development were realized mainly in the structure of the institutes of the Academy of Sciences, and only with rare exceptions the research function was realized in higher education institutions (e.g., Moscow State University (MSU), Leningrad (now St. Petersburg) State University, Moscow Engineering Physics Institute (MEPhI), and Novosibirsk State University (NSU)).

The next stage in the development of the right to education in Russia is associated with the collapse of the USSR and the reforms that began in the early 1990-s in all aspects of public life, including education.

The first post-Soviet decade was characterized by a "policy of non-interference". After the adoption of the main federal laws on education in the early 1990-s, the possibilities of state policy in the field of higher education were determined by the general economic situation in the country.

The period of institutional transformations of the 2000s in the Russian education system began with a fundamentally new for the country system of assessing the quality of general education based on the Uniform State Examination (USE), which inevitably affected the system of higher education, since the USE is a standardized examination in individual subjects, which is mandatory for all school leavers, and its results become at the same time the conditions for admission to higher education. The first experiments on the introduction of the USE in some regions of Russia began in 2001; its participants were the Republic of Chuvashia, the Republic of Mari El, the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia), Samara and Rostov regions, where the exam was conducted in eight academic disciplines. In 2001, only 50 state higher education institutions started accepting applicants based on the results of the USE (internal examinations were also retained in higher education institutions). From 2001 to 2008, the number of regions participating in the experiment and universities accepting students based on the USE results increased annually. During this period, the regions independently established a specific list of subjects for which the USE was conducted. In 2009, the exam was introduced as a compulsory exam throughout the country.

The government also encouraged other institutional reforms, such as joining the Bologna Process and the integration of education and science.

Although the Russian Federation's intention to join the Bologna Process faced strong opposition from university administrators and faculty, as well as students and parents, Russia signed the Bologna Declaration in 2003. Since 2009, all educational programs (with some exceptions) had to switch to two levels (bachelor's and master's degrees).

The structural direction of reforms in this period was related to the creation of several groups of universities of a new type, which were to solve the problems of science and innovation development, socio-economic development of industries and territories. One of the first steps in this direction was the decree of the Government of the Russian Federation of September 17, 2001 "On university complexes" adopted in 2001.

The creation of a university complex was supposed to unite educational organizations of various levels of training among themselves, as well as with other institutions and non-profit organizations.

Another structural initiative was a special measure of the federal target program of education development for 2006-2010, which envisaged the development of professional educational institutions implementing programs at various levels of education.

As part of this task, some secondary vocational education institutions became part of higher education institutions, which began to implement and develop relevant programs.

In the fall of 2005, at the meeting of the President with the Government of the Russian Federation, the task was set to create a new type of higher education institutions, which were to become centers of regional development and attraction of talented young people, key agents in the development of innovative activities in the region.

In 2018, the national project "Education" was adopted for 2019-2024. The project is aimed at ensuring the global competitiveness of Russian education and placing the Russian Federation among the world's top 10 countries in terms of the quality of general education, as well as fostering a harmoniously developed and socially responsible personality based on the spiritual and moral values of the peoples of the Russian Federation, historical and national-cultural traditions. The project involves the implementation of four main areas of development of the education system: updating its content, creating the necessary modern infrastructure, training professional staff, their retraining and professional development, as well as the creation of the most effective mechanisms for managing this sphere.

In May 2022, Valery Falkov, the head of the Ministry of Education and Science, announced Russia's plans to withdraw from the Bologna Process, which envisages a two-tier education system - bachelor's and master's degrees. Already in November, the ministry proposed to separate specialization. Speaking about the development of the education system in his address to the Federal Assembly on February 21, 2023, Russian President Vladimir Putin suggested returning to the traditional four to six years of study at universities. At the same time, he emphasized that the transition to the new education system should be smooth.

IV. CONCLUSION

In general, the reform of higher education in Russia in 2023-2024 is going in the direction of modernization and adaptation to modern requirements. Increasing the practical component of education, updating curricula - all these changes are aimed at creating a more flexible and competitive higher education system in Russia. In the coming years, we can expect further development of these changes and strengthening of the quality of education, which will help students to enter the working environment faster and more effectively.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ СИСТЕМЫ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В РОССИИ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается система высшего образования в России через которую передается культурный опыт, способствующий накоплению интеллектуального и духовного потенциалов. Показано, что модель системы образования обусловлена не только потребностями социальной реальности и стратегическими целями общества, но и несет в себе историческую память о ее развитии и становлении. Поэтому в процессе социальной трансформации выбор наиболее адекватной модели, отвечающей как внутренним, так и внешним потребностям государства, является важной задачей, направленной на создание четко функционирующего механизма, формирующего тип личности, отвечающий заданному социальному заказу.

Ключевые слова: образование, личность, заказ, память, история.

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